

Editorial

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It is with pleasure that we present Volume 2 of the *University of Sydney Journal of TESOL*. This volume features a broad range of topics, methodologies, and perspectives within the TESOL field, showcasing the multifaceted nature of TESOL research and practice. The contributions within this volume demonstrate a shared emphasis on innovation and enhancement within the field of TESOL. From pioneering pedagogical approaches to the integration of emerging technologies, each contribution shows a commitment to advancing the efficacy and impact of TESOL.

OVERVIEW OF THIS VOLUME

Reports of original research

David Gutteridge explores the disparities between teachers' perceived and actual approaches to incorporating Australian English in ELICOS classrooms. Using data from a teacher survey ($n = 21$) and follow-up interviews ($n = 6$), the study reveals teachers' awareness and strategic decisions regarding classroom practices. Thematic analysis of qualitative responses suggests that while teachers make nuanced language decisions, they may not be aware of such decisions. This study underscores the need for teacher professional development in the area of the different varieties of English and reflexivity in practice.

Jialiang He examines the effectiveness of the *Praat* Program in enhancing English pronunciation among Chinese university students learning English as a foreign language (EFL). Pronunciation, a crucial aspect of spoken language for conveying intended meanings, often poses challenges to Chinese EFL students due to limited practice and feedback. In a six-week study involving 18 participants, significant

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pronunciation improvement was observed after *Praat* training. Qualitative findings underscore *Praat's* role in providing valuable feedback and a stress-free learning environment that contribute to enhancing students' pronunciation skills.

Discussion articles

Jack C. Richards focuses on the complexities surrounding the use of English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) for teaching academic subjects. The paper is structured around eight key questions: (1) Reasons for adopting EMI; (2) Nature of EMI; (3) Language demands of teaching in EMI; (4) Teachers' views on their primary role and responsibility in EMI; (5) Impact of EMI on teachers; (6) EMI teacher professional identity; (7) EMI learner; and (8) Strategies for developing academic literacy among students.

Keith Cheng Lin draws on research on the Noticing Hypothesis to help improve English learners' awareness of language forms. The paper discusses research on input enhancement and external/internal factors influencing the quality of learners' noticing. This article introduces a synthesised method of form-focused instruction that incorporates input enhancement and other techniques. It provides suggestions for future classroom research.

Pedagogical practices

Shogo Yamamoto highlights the significance of incorporating various modes of communication in English language classrooms beyond traditional language use. The article argues for a multimodal perspective in considering classroom space to promote communicative language teaching. Through a Japanese public high school classroom example, Yamamoto examines how traditional spaces often support didactic, teacher-centred pedagogy. The author suggests leveraging modes and technologies to empower students and enhance teachers' professional development. The article emphasises the importance of teachers' awareness of utilising semiotic modes and technologies to enhance language teaching and learning in classroom settings.

Adam Steinhoff presents an application of a genre-based approach (GBA) for teaching writing in both ESL and EFL contexts. The paper discusses the pedagogical applications and theoretical background of GBA and reviews existing research. Three lesson plans are outlined: two on email writing to recommend a job (Lesson Plans 1 and 2) and one on recipe writing (Lesson Plan 3). The paper includes guidelines to aid teachers in implementing these lesson plans.

Interview

Aek Phakiti interviews Professor Ken Cruickshank regarding his enthusiasm for TESOL, his current research projects, and the significant impact of his Institute for Language Community Education. Professor Cruickshank offers invaluable advice for PhD students, emphasising strategies for maintaining motivation in academia. Furthermore, he provides insightful guidance for TESOL coursework students and educators.

Book review

Finally, in her review of Lindy Woodrow's (2022) book "Introducing Researching English for Specific Purposes," *Louise Kaktins* applauds this book as a useful resource for delving into critical research aspects within the essential realm of English language teaching. She underscores Woodrow's contribution as a foundational guide for aspiring English for Specific Purposes researchers. Kaktins notes Woodrow's meticulous organisation of the book, lauding her efforts to demystify complex concepts and facilitating students' progression from interns to independent researchers.